

Optimization of Food Delivery Routes and Distribution Costs Using the Nearest Neighbor in PT. XYZ

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Abstract

Transportation is a very important means in supporting the successful distribution of goods, especially for companies that have *outlets*. Transportation problems often occur in the process of distributing goods that are not appropriate and less than optimal, so that from these problems the company experiences a very high cost of distributing goods. By using the transportation model, the company can reduce the cost of product distribution and distribution channels to be more optimal. At the company PT. XYZ distribution activities are very important considering the company has *outlets*. Product distribution that is less than optimal in distribution is one of the problems that must be faced, many problems occur in product distribution routes that are less than optimal, so product delivery costs are very high. This study aims to measure the efficiency of the distribution route so as to produce an optimal product distribution route based on the value of the shortest mileage and minimize product delivery costs. The method used in the problem of determining the distribution route is *Nearest neighbor*. Data collection was carried out in 4 areas of the island of Java consisting of West Java, Greater Jakarta, Central Java and East Java with a total of 32 *outlets*. The distance traveled in one distribution is 8,030,80 km with a total cost of Rp. 30,604,264. Based on the results obtained from the calculation of the fastest total mileage using the *Nearest neighbor* which is passed by *driver* the distribution XYZ produces fewer routes than before using the method. The total distance using the *Nearest Neighbor* is 4,501.7 km with a distance savings of 3,529.1 km or a percentage of 44%. Likewise, the total distribution costs became Rp 16,990,185 with cost savings of Rp 13,614,078 or a percentage of 44%. From these results, it is expected that PT. XYZ can apply the *Nearest neighbor* method to determine the shortest path and the minimum cost.

Keywords: *Distribution Routes, Nearest neighbors, Transportation, Cost Reduction.*

INTRODUCTION

PT. XYZ was founded in 2004, is a subsidiary of PT. HIJ. PT. XYZ has extensive expertise in manufacturing EOM for baked goods and traditional snack products Brand Toast whose products are renowned for their delicious taste and long shelf life which have become a popular choice for visitors to HIJ retail stores. PT. XYZ also provides private label manufacturing services for major retail players in Indonesia such as Alfamart & Hypermart.

Products from PT. XYZ has received a halal certificate from the MUI in West Java and has been certified by the POM. Currently PT. XYZ has been selling its products throughout Indonesia and is in the development stage to sell its products overseas. To ensure better quality, PT. XYZ is also in the process of applying for an ISO 22000 certificate.

Distribution is one aspect of marketing at PT. XYZ. Distribution can be interpreted as a marketing activity that is used to facilitate and facilitate the delivery of goods and services from producers to consumers, so that their use is as needed based on the type, quantity, price, place and when needed. The number of product requests from various regions, such as on the island of Java, there are 32 *outlets* spread out. In its distribution, PT. XYZ divides 4 shipping routes, namely West Java, Greater Jakarta, Central Java and East Java. Each delivery route uses 2 trucks. When heading to the delivery route, *driver* only distributes products according to the list *outlets* provided by the company, there is no determination of the delivery route that must be passed first, so the distribution process is still not optimal.

Based on the conditions experienced by the company PT. XYZ in distributing its products, it is necessary to do research to determine the optimal delivery route that can reduce the distance traveled and transportation costs. In this study, a method is used to determine the minimum route or the shortest route, namely the *Nearest neighbor*. By doing this research, it is hoped that it can produce optimal shipping routes and cut transportation costs at PT. XYZ. Therefore, the author conducted a study with the title "Optimization of Food Delivery Distribution Routes and Costs". Using the *Nearest Neighbor* at PT. XYZ".

LITERATURE REVIEW

Logistics Management

Logistics management is part of the supply chain process that functions to plan, implement, and control the efficient and effective storage and flow of goods, services and related information from the point of origin to the point of consumption in order to meet customer needs (Lambert, 2004).

Transportation and Distribution

Distribution and transportation management generally performs a number of basic functions, namely segmenting and determining service level targets, determining the mode of transportation to be used, consolidating information and delivery, scheduling and determining delivery routes, providing value-added services, storing inventory, and handling returns (Pujawan, 2010).

Transportation Cost

Transportation costs are costs needed in the transportation process, these costs are caused by the use of special facilities or unexpected costs that arise to support transportation needs.

Fixed Costs and Variable

Costs Transportation costs are categorized into two, namely fixed costs and variable costs. Fixed costs are costs whose amount does not change due to changes in the output of an activity. While variable costs are costs whose amount varies with changes in output.

Vehicle Operating Costs (BOK)

Vehicle Operating Costs (BOK) are variables that are considered important in calculating vehicle operating costs (Tamin, 2000):

1. Fixed Costs
2. Variable Costs
3. Asset Ownership Costs

Vehicle Routing Problem

Vehicle routing problem (VRP) a delivery or distribution problem that involves a set of vehicle routes centered on one or more depots to serve customers spread across various regions according to their respective requests (Vaidyanathan et al., 1999; Vigo, 2002):

1. Minimizing overall travel costs
2. Minimizing the number of vehicles used
3. Balancing routes
4. Minimizing customer complaints

Methods Nearest Neighbor

Algorithm *algorithms* include heuristic methods implemented in the *vehicle routing problem*, problem solving techniques applied to the *Nearest Neighbor*, namely starting from p determination of the starting point and continued by determining the closest point. The method of solving problems with the *Nearest Neighbor* is considered to be able to produce effective solutions (Johnson, D. L; Bentley JL, 1997).

The procedure for implementing the Nearest Neighbor algorithm method (Pop et al., 2011) is as follows:

1. Distribution starts from the warehouse, then a location search is carried out by finding the nearest customer location that has not been visited by the distributor from the starting point.
2. The distribution process is continued to another customer place that has the closest distance from the previously selected point.
 - a. If there is a customer selected as the next location but there is remaining capacity in the transport vehicle, then the process returns to step (2).
 - b. If the delivery capacity on the vehicle runs out, then the process returns to step (1).
 - c. If no customer is selected because the delivery capacity exceeds the vehicle capacity, then return to step (1).
 - d. The process starts again from the warehouse and visits customers that have not been visited and have the closest distance.
 - e. If the customer has been visited entirely then the distribution process is complete.

METHODS

Stages of research are described in the flow chart as follows:

Figure 1 Research Stages

The flowchart description above is as follows:

1. Problem Identification
The problems that occur in PT. XYZ is the distance traveled is very far and the costs incurred in the process of distributing the product to each *outlet* of each region are quite large.
2. Problem Solving
Model The model used in problem solving that has been identified is the *Nearest Neighbor* by minimizing mileage and distribution process costs.
3. Primary Data
collection by interviewing informants to find out data on company profiles, customer data and product demand, vehicle types and the number of vehicles used to distribute products to each *outlet* and data on the distance from the depot to each delivery location.
4. Secondary Data
Secondary data is used to support primary data, where secondary data is a source of research data obtained by researchers indirectly through intermediary media. Secondary data in this study were obtained from other written data related to research such as data on the number of product shipments to each *outlet* every day, literature and other document data.
5. Data Processing
Data processing and analysis uses the *Nearest Neighbor* to determine the shortest route as the optimal route solution by minimizing costs.
6. Analysis
The analysis was conducted to determine the final result of using the *Nearest Neighbor* and as a comparison of the total distance and costs incurred before and after using the *Nearest neighbors*.

7. Conclusion

The conclusion is made by analyzing the results of the analysis of the use of the *Nearest Neighbor* in optimizing distribution routes at PT. XYZ to prove the effect of *Nearest Neighbor*.

The following is data on product distribution to several *customers* which have been grouped into several cities.

Table 1 Customer Data

Destination	Code	Destination	Code
Cicalengka	K1	Cirebon	K9
Nanjung	K2	Indramayu	K10
Padjajaran	K3	Cicendo	K11
Padalarang	K4	Cinambo	K12
Tasikmalaya	K5	Ciumbuleuit	K13
Kopo Permai	K6	Cianjur	K14
Arcamanik	K7	Tangerang	K15
Lembang	K8	Bekasi	K16
Cikarang	K17	Semarang	K25
Karawang	K18	Tegal	K26
Cibitung	K19	Cilacap	K27
Bogor	K20	Surabaya	K28
Jakarta	K21	Malang	K29
Surakarta	K22	Jember	K30
Klaten	K23	Sidoarjo	K31
Yogyakarta	K24	Gresik	K32

(Source: Data Observation)

The cities were grouped into 4 parts, namely West Java, Greater Jakarta, Central Java and East Java, each area using 2 trucks with random allocation of some areas to other areas as follows;

Table 2 Initial Route

Area	Consumer	Distance (km)
West Java	G-K2-K6-K3-K7-K8-K4-K1-K5-G	319,7
	G-K11-K12-K13-K14-K9-K10-G	599,1
Greater Jakarta	G-K20-K15-K21-K16-G	460,6
	G-K17-K18-K19-G	301,1
Central Java	G-K27-K25-K26-G	988,0
	G-K22-K24-K23-G	1760,0
East Java	G-K30-K28-K29-G	1621,3
	G-K31-K32-G	1981,0

(Source: Data Observation)

Details of costs with the initial route using 8 trucks with each regional destination use 2 cars.

Table 3 Details of Total Shipping

Area	Consumer	Biaya Transportasi Awal				Total
		Distance (km)	Meals	Costs Fuel	Levies	
West Java	G-K2-K6-K3-K7-K8-K4-K1-K5-G	319,7	Rp479.550	Rp379.644	Rp250.000	Rp1.109.194
	G-K11-K12-K13-K14-K9-K10-G	599,1	Rp898.650	Rp711.431	Rp250.000	Rp1.860.081
Greater Jakarta	G-K20-K15-K21-K16-G	460,6	Rp690.900	Rp546.963	Rp764.133	Rp2.001.996
	G-K17-K18-K19-G	301,1	Rp451.650	Rp357.556	Rp551.467	Rp1.360.673
Central Java	G-K27-K25-K26-G	988,0	Rp1.482.000	Rp1.173.250	Rp1.247.778	Rp3.903.028
	G-K22-K24-K23-G	1760,0	Rp2.640.000	Rp2.090.000	Rp1.955.556	Rp6.685.556
East Java	G-K30-K28-K29-G	1621,3	Rp2.431.950	Rp1.925.294	Rp1.801.444	Rp6.158.688
	G-K31-K32-G	1981,0	Rp2.971.500	Rp2.352.438	Rp2.201.111	Rp7.525.049
Total		8030,8	-	-	-	Rp30.604.264

(Source: Data Observation)

Route determination using the *Nearest Neighbor* starts from the warehouse with the address Cigondewah.

a. West Java

- Iteration 1

Table 4 Iteration 1 West Java

Code	Iteration 1	Distance
K1	Cicalengka	39,7
K2	Nanjung	6
K3	Padjajaran	5,4
K4	Padalarang	19,9
K5	Tasikmalaya	150
K6	Kopo	9,8
K7	Arcamanik	23,7
K8	Lembang	18,8
K9	Cirebon	207
K10	Indramayu	217
K11	Cicendo	6
K12	Cinambo	22
K13	Ciumbuleuit	10,5
K14	Cianjur	62

(Source: Data Observation)

- Iteration 3

Table 6 Iteration 3 West Java

Code	Iteration 3	Distance
K1	Cicalengka	35,4
K2	Nanjung	11,6
K4	Padalarang	8,4
K5	Tasikmalaya	119
K6	Kopo	9,1
K7	Arcamanik	12
K8	Lembang	14,1
K9	Cirebon	208
K10	Indramayu	218
K11	Cicendo	0
K12	Cinambo	13,6
K13	Ciumbuleuit	5,8
K14	Cianjur	62,4

- Iteration 5

Table 8 Iteration 5 West Java

Code	Iteration 5	Distance
K1	Cicalengka	29,2
K2	Nanjung	16,6
K4	Padalarang	0
K5	Tasikmalaya	111
K6	Kopo	11,5
K7	Arcamanik	4,4
K8	Lembang	19,1
K9	Cirebon	212
K10	Indramayu	223
K12	Cinambo	8,8
K14	Cianjur	67,8

- Iteration 7

Code	Iteration 7	Distance
K1	Cicalengka	20,4
K2	Nanjung	28,9

- Iteration 2

Table 5 Iteration 2 West Java

Code	Iteration 2	Distance
K1	Cicalengka	42,3
K2	Nanjung	10,9
K3	Padjajaran	0
K4	Padalarang	8,5
K5	Tasikmalaya	12,5
K6	Kopo	13,2
K7	Arcamanik	11,3
K8	Lembang	13,4
K9	Cirebon	207
K10	Indramayu	217
K11	Cicendo	1,1
K12	Cinambo	13,9
K13	Ciumbuleuit	5,1
K14	Cianjur	61,7

- Iteration 4

Table 7

Iteration 4 West Java

(Source: Processing Data)

Code	Iteration 4	Distance
K1	Cicalengka	37,8
K2	Nanjung	13,5
K4	Padalarang	9,7
K5	Tasikmalaya	134
K6	Kopo	22,1
K7	Arcamanik	12,5
K8	Lembang	10
K9	Cirebon	151
K10	Indramayu	220
K12	Cinambo	17,4
K13	Ciumbuleuit	0
K14	Cianjur	64,4

- Iteration 6

Table 9 Iteration 6 West Java

(Source: Data Observation)

Code	Iteration 6	Distance
K1	Cicalengka	25,5
K2	Nanjung	20,4
K5	Tasikmalaya	108
K6	Kopo	15,3
K7	Arcamanik	0
K8	Lembang	22,9
K9	Cirebon	216
K10	Indramayu	134
K12	Cinambo	5,1
K14	Cianjur	71,2

- Iteration 8

K5	Tasikmalaya	103
K6	Kopo	14,9
K8	Lembang	28,8
K9	Cirebon	124
K10	Indramayu	129
K12	Cinambo	0
K14	Cianjur	76,1

Iteration 8 West Java
(Source: Data Observation)

- Iteration 9

Table 12 Iteration 9 West Java

Code	Iteration 9	Distance
K1	Cicalengka	44,9
K2	Nanjung	0
K5	Tasikmalaya	127
K8	Lembang	22,7
K9	Cirebon	202
K10	Indramayu	213
K14	Cianjur	56,5

- Iteration 11

Table 14 Iteration 11 West Java

Code	Iteration 11	Distance
K1	Cicalengka	0
K5	Tasikmalaya	83,1
K9	Cirebon	116
K10	Indramayu	121
K14	Cianjur	92

(Source: Data Observation)

- Iteration 13

Table 16 Iteration 13 West Java

Code	Iteration 13	Distance
K9	Cirebon	0
K10	Indramayu	51,9
K14	Cianjur	239

(Source: Data Observation)

b. Greater Jakarta

- Iteration 1

Table 4. 18 Iteration 1 Greater Jakarta

Code	Iteration 1	Distance
k15	Tangerang	179
k16	Bekasi	125
k17	Cikarang	117
k18	Karawang	87,3
k19	Cibitung	115
k20	Bogor	169
k21	Jakarta	152

(Source: Data Observation)

- Iteration 3

Table 20 Iteration 3 Greater Jakarta

Code	Iteration 3	Distance
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Table 11

Table 10 Iteration 7 West Java

Code	Iteration 8	Distance
K1	Cicalengka	361
K2	Nanjung	16,7
K5	Tasikmalaya	103
K6	Kopo	0
K8	Lembang	21,6
K9	Cirebon	210
K10	Indramayu	220
K14	Cianjur	64

- Iteration 10

Table 13 Iteration 10 West Java

(Source: Data Observation)

Code	Iteration 10	Distance
K1	Cicalengka	44,7
K5	Tasikmalaya	142
K8	Lembang	0
K9	Cirebon	142
K10	Indramayu	153
K14	Cianjur	66,4

- Iteration 12

Table 15 Iteration 12 West Java

Code	Iteration 12	Distance
K5	Tasikmalaya	0
K9	Cirebon	113
K10	Indramayu	152
K14	Cianjur	178

- Iteration 14

Table 17 Iteration 14 West Java

Code	Iteration 13	Distance
K10	Indramayu	0
K14	Cianjur	248

- Iteration 2

Table 4. 19 Iteration 2 Greater Jakarta

Code	Iteration 2	Distance
k15	Tangerang	103
k16	Bekasi	48,4
k17	Cikarang	24,9
k18	Karawang	0
k19	Cibitung	38,5
k20	Bogor	92,3
k21	Jakarta	86,6

- Iteration 4

Table 21 Iteration 4 Greater Jakarta

Code	Iteration 4	Distance
k15	Tangerang	77,4
k16	Bekasi	18,2
k17	Cikarang	0
k19	Cibitung	9,9
k20	Bogor	67,9
k21	Jakarta	58,9

(Source: Data Observation)

Code	Iteration 5	Distance
k15	Tangerang	62,5
k16	Bekasi	0
k20	Bogor	53
k21	Jakarta	46,3

- Iteration 5

Table 22 Iteration 5 Greater Jakarta

Code	Iteration 6	Distance
k15	Tangerang	68,3
k16	Bekasi	14,2
k19	Cibitung	0
k20	Bogor	58,8
k21	Jakarta	50,7

- Iteration 6

Table 23 Iteration 6 Greater Jakarta

Code	Iteration 7	Distance
k15	Tangerang	0
k20	Bogor	75,3

(Source: Data Observation)

- Iteration 7

Table 24 Iteration 7 Greater Jakarta

Code	Iteration 1	Distance
K27	Cilacap	262
K26	Tegal	285
K25	Semarang	438
K22	Surakarta	529
K23	Klaten	529
K24	Yogyakarta	547

(Source: Data Observation)

c. Central Java

- Iteration 1

Table 25 Iteration 1 Central Java

Code	Iteration 2	Distance
K27	Cilacap	0
K26	Tegal	119
K25	Semarang	277
K22	Surakarta	242
K23	Klaten	223
K24	Yogyakarta	186

- Iteration 2

Table 26 Iteration 2 Central Java

Kode	Iterasi 3	Jarak
K26	Tegal	0
K25	Semarang	159
K22	Surakarta	250
K23	Klaten	250
K24	Yogyakarta	268

(Source: Data Observation)

- Iteration 3

Table 27 Iteration 3 Central Java

Code	Iteration 4	Distance
K25	Semarang	0
K22	Surakarta	101
K23	Klaten	103
K24	Yogyakarta	121

- Iteration 4

Table 28 Iteration 4 Central Java

Code	Iteration 5	Distance
K22	Surakarta	0
K23	Klaten	21,7
K24	Yogyakarta	53,1

(Source: Data Observation)

- Iteration 5

Table 29 Iteration 5 Central Java

Code	Iteration 6	Distance
K23	Klaten	0
K24	Yogyakarta	35,4

(Source: Data Observation)

- Iteration 6

Table 30 Iteration 6 Central Java

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d. East Java

- Iteration 1

Table 31 Iteration 1 East Java

Code	Iteration 1	Distance
K31	Sidoarjo	770
K28	Surabaya	774
K32	Gresik	780
K29	Malang	840
K30	Jember	939

(Source: Data Observation)

- Iteration 2

Table 32 Iteration 2 East Java

Code	Iteration 2	Distance
K31	Sidoarjo	0
K28	Surabaya	21.3
K32	Gresik	38.8
K29	Malang	77.6
K30	Jember	177

- Iteration 3

Table 33 Iteration 3 East Java

Code	Iteration 3	Distance
K28	Surabaya	0
K32	Gresik	23.4
K29	Malang	91.4
K30	Jember	191

Observation)

- Iteration 4

Table 34 Iteration 4 East Java

(Source:

Code	Iteration 4	Distance
K32	Gresik	0
K29	Malang	112
K30	Jember	211

Data

- Iteration 5

Table 35 Iteration 5 East Java

Code	Iteration 5	Distance
K29	Malang	0
K30	Jember	193

Table 36 Recapitulation of Cost Savings and Distribution Channels
Transportation Costs

Area	Consumer	Distance (km)	Meals	Costs Fuel	Distribution Cost	Total
West Java	G-K3-K11-K13-K4-K7-K12-K6-K2-K8-K1-K5-K9-K10-K14-G	687,8	Rp1.031.700	Rp816.763	Rp250.000	Rp2.098.463
Greater Jakarta	G-K6-K1-K7-K2-K3-K4-K5-G	468,9	Rp703.350	Rp556.819	Rp625.200	Rp1.885.369
Central Java	G-K27-K26-K25-K22-K23-K24-G	1288	Rp1.932.000	Rp1.529.500	Rp1.581.111	Rp5.042.611
East Java	G-K31-K28-K32-K29-K30-G	2057	Rp3.085.500	Rp2.442.688	Rp2.435.556	Rp7.963.743
Total		4501,7	-	-	-	Rp16.990.185

(Source: Data Observation)

Table 37 Table of Accumulated Distance and Cost

Remarks	Initial	Savings	Difference	Percentage
Distance	8030,8	4501,7	3529,1	44%
Cost	Rp30.604.264	Rp16.990.185	Rp13.614.078	44%

(Source: Data Observation)

The table above is the result of accumulated costs before and after calculation using the *Nearest Neighbor*, before using the *Nearest Neighbor* the total distance traveled by the expedition team was 8030.8 KM at a cost of Rp. 30,604,264, while after applying the *Nearest Neighbor* the total distance traveled was reduced by 3529.1 KM to 4501.7 KM and the costs incurred were reduced by Rp. 13,614,078, - to Rp. 16,990,185, -. Based on these calculations, it can be seen that both in terms of cost and in terms of distance, the effectiveness is 44%.

CONCLUSION

The results of observations of PT. XYZ shows that PT. XYZ has not optimized the shipping route, so the company incurs quite a lot of costs and has a long shipping route in one shipment. To optimize distance and shipping costs, PT.XYZ can use the Nearest Neighbor method to optimize routes and optimize costs for the company. Optimization using the Nearest Neighbor Method, the company can optimize distance and cost savings by 44%. The distance savings resulting from savings with the Nearest Neighbor method are obtained from 8030.80 KM to 4501.70 KM. This optimization reduces the distribution distance by 3529.1 KM with a percentage of 44% and obtained cost savings resulting from savings with the Nearest Neighbor Method, namely from Rp. 30,604,264 to Rp. 16,990,185. This optimization reduces the distribution distance by Rp. 13,614,078.00 with a percentage of 44%.

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